

**AESTHETIC VIEWS OF PIRIMQUL KADIROV: THE
HARMONY OF CREATIVITY AND SKILL**
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ANNOTATION: This article briefly highlights the aesthetic views of Pirimkul Kadyrov, his works, articles written as a literary critic and theorist, publicist, his opinions on literature and creativity. Literary and aesthetic views are conditionally divided into groups and their specific features are analyzed.

Key words: aesthetic ideal, criticism, scientific treatise, historical and scientific novel, journalist, modernism, spirituality, artistic language, scientific art, journalistic article, creative concept.

It is known from the world of literature that the creative concept, aesthetic credo, and goal of a creative person can be understood not only from his artistic works, but also from his literary and theoretical views, articles and critical opinions. "It is known from the experience of world literary studies that the literary-theoretical views of writers or poets play an important role in the interpretation of artistic works. Therefore, the views of great talents on poetry, art, talented people, literature and art in general are published in the form of special books. The importance of such works is obvious in two ways: First of all, the artist's artistic and aesthetic concept will be known. Secondly, the treasury of literary-theoretical views is enriched and serves as a school of example for those who are entering the field of literature." ¹ says literary scholar B. Karimov. An artist can express his creative concept not only through artistic works, but also through literary and critical articles, as well as scientific books and pamphlets reflecting his literary and theoretical views. However, both a single literary-critical

¹ Bahodir Karim. "Erkin Vohidovning estetik qarashlariga bir nazar" kh-davron.uz

article and a scientific-theoretical treatise should be written with inspiration, have a unique internal structure, and be a reflection of the creative talent. They also have artistry, writing style and aesthetic idea. After all, the creator directly expresses his literary-aesthetic and critical views as a writer, a poet, a person of creativity in general, he writes with inspiration, and his soul lies in him. As the well-known literary critic Bahadir Karim said, "creativity is an extremely individual process. This process can be different for everyone. There are no axioms for the creative process. The only rule of the creative process is writing. The other is imagination. The other is redundant. The meeting of a poet or a writer with a white paper - if truly beautiful and eternal works are born - is really a huge celebration. Otherwise it is nothing but a waste of life. It is the artist's responsibility to understand, recognize and share the lessons of this experience with others." As the writer's aesthetic ideal and artistic idea, his aesthetic concept emerges in the creative process, the literary-aesthetic views of the creator also surface in the creative process. That is, the theoretical views of the creator emerge in this process. As we travel through the famous Uzbek writer Pirmkul Kadirov's creative field, we will see different colors. Nationalism, universalism, modernity and historicity are mixed in his creative laboratory. Pirmkul Kadirov is one of the creators who has a special place in Uzbek literature with his historical novels, dramatic works, epics, translations, historical-educational works, literary-critical, educational articles, journalistic works. We found it necessary to study the writer's literary-critical, scientific, journalistic work, which includes his literary-aesthetic views, conditionally divided into the following four groups.

1. Treatises on language.
2. Historical-scientific art
3. Literary thoughts
3. Literary-critical and journalistic articles, interviews.

These works are united by the imagination of the writer about the mysterious world hidden in the mosaic layers and the harmony of artistry, correspondingly unique views, most importantly, selflessness, feelings of love for the Motherland and its history.

There is a world of wisdom in P. Kadirov's theoretical views born from his life and creative experiences. Adib paid special attention to language problems in his research. It is not wrong to say that the thoughts of the writer about the artistic language are deeply approached, scientifically based aesthetic views. The compilation of several years of theories about language was reflected in Pirimkul Kadirov's works "Language and El", "People's Language and Realistic Prose". These pamphlets show how important the artistic language is for the artistic work, in showing the style of the writer, as well as the mentality and customs of the nation.

The author interprets "Language and El" as scientific fiction, and of course there is truth in it. As he approaches the analysis of the problems of the Uzbek literary language from a historical point of view, the research method does not remain within the framework of pure linguistics. In particular, from "Bilga Khagan" and "Kultegin" to "Alp Er Tong'a War Chronicle", "Qutadgu Bilig", "Devonu Lug'otut Turk" and Yassavi's Wisdom, Khorezmi's "Love Book", Sayfi Palace in his works, he studies, analyzes and compares the linguistic features of historical-literary masterpieces up to the Timurid period. The author's observations about language are easy to read as if reading a work of art, they are conveyed to the reader in understandable words, so that both a scholar of literature and an ordinary reader can understand the true purpose of the writer.

Pirimkul Kadirov has been working tirelessly for many years on his scientific research called "People's language and realistic prose". To be honest, in the last sixty years, the ideological content, visual means, and artistic language of Uzbek Soviet literature have experienced great quality changes. As the writer himself noted: "researching this complex and multifaceted process, uncovering its internal mechanism is very necessary for the further

development of our literature and literary language." The writer's work "Vernacular language and realistic prose" shows the importance of extremely rich vernacular language in the formation of Uzbek realistic prose and the establishment of Uzbek realism. will be done." Although the focus of "Language and People" is the study of the problems of the formation of the classic Uzbek literary language, the author did not limit himself to this issue. He often refers to our history in general, in particular to the history of our literature, culture, and spirituality, to some events that are not so well known to many people, but to the fate of our great ancestors and to some events that played an important role in our history. draws our attention, expresses his independent attitude to some controversial points related to them, and thus sheds light on some problems. All of this comes back and, in the end, combined with considerations and conclusions about the formation of our Uzbek classical literary language, decision-making processes, gives a strange compositional integrity and harmony to scientific and artistic works.²

Looking at the aesthetic views of Pirimkul Kadyrov, the writer said, "Geologists look for things of high value and precious things, not of low value and worthless things, wandering through the mountains and deserts. "Similarly, the spiritual searches of a person are focused on the blessings that are dear to him and satisfy his spiritual needs." In fact, as a result of Pirimkul Kadyrov's research, no works of low value came to the world. All his works are "valuable works that serve for the spiritual perfection of man and satisfy his spiritual needs. In 2007, we had the opportunity to read the scientific-historical work of such a writer, who serves for the spiritual perfection of a person, entitled "The figure of Amir Temur". In the description of the youth and teenage years of Adib Sahibgiron, he emphasizes that Amir Temur's achievement of the rank of a great scholar is not without reason, and refers to many historical sources that justify his love of reading books and great respect for scholars. In this work, Pirimkul Kadirov shows that he is not only a

² B.Nazarov. "Til qadri". Sharq yulduzi jurnali. 2006-yil, 1-son, 138-139-betlar.

writer, but also a clever historian. The scientific essence of the work "The figure of Amir Temur" is added to the artistic interpretation: it creates a whole scientific and artistic essence. P. Kadirov takes the activities and nature of living, dynamic people as the basis and basis for scientific analysis and artistic interpretation.

Pirimkul Kadyrov's work "The figure of Amir Temur" is a work of art created in a combination of science and art. It is noteworthy that in this scientific work, special attention is paid to the issue of the spiritual environment, which is a necessary factor in the development of a great figure like Amir Temur. The fact that the writer Amir Temur studied life and work, the history of that time with great love and presented it to the reader in a lively, simple and sincere language is certainly worthy of praise. In the mid-sixties, the stories of Pirimkul Kadyrov called "Literary Thoughts" began to be published in newspapers and magazines. It can be said without exaggeration that the writer's thoughts - his subtle observations, the depth of his literary observations, the richness of his opinions - suddenly attracted the attention of the literary public. Adib explains the reason for turning to the genre of "Literary Thoughts" and writes that "it is not the result of skill, but the result of the need for skill." In his literary thoughts, Pirimkul Kadyrov also talks about truths that are obvious to everyone at first glance. But the truths mentioned by the writer: life and literary knowledge, real talent, the problem of the hero, issues of literary language have not lost their importance even today. The best means of making a work interesting is that its theme and idea, its characters and plot, its artistic texture and style are unique and can give something new." While reading "Literary Thoughts", it is not difficult for the reader to notice that the writer defends the principles arising from his creative experience. When a writer studies life, he must find important and new aspects of it that no one has described yet. Only for this he should know literature very well. Because a person who is not fully aware of what is included in the literature and what is not included in life, may be busy saying

that he will invent a new cart. Literary studies often say that the deeper and deeper the critical thinking of an artist is, the stronger his literary talent is. In fact, the critical opinions reflected in Pirimkul Kadyrov's novel "Literary Thoughts" show how high his talent is. Pirimkul Kadyrov has a series of articles that can be considered literary-critical, historical-educational conversations and journalistic. A number of literary and critical articles of the writer have their place in the world of literature. The thoughts and ideas expressed in them are the words of a real talent, a smart critic, a sharp-thinking scientist. His critical article titled "Spirituality, Modernism and Absurdity" published in the 12th issue of 2004 of the newspaper "Literature and Art of Uzbekistan", which reflects the characteristics of "modernism", which has formed as a separate current in world literature. It is not wrong to say that it made a sharp turn in the world of Uzbek literature. Speaking about spirituality and aesthetics in the article, Pirimkul Kadirov says that literature first of all gives a person spiritual nourishment, aesthetic pleasure, delights his soul and mind; "All nature is alive with sunlight. But a person is not limited to enjoying the sunlight. The human soul also feels a great need for spiritual intelligence that radiates from the words, images, and works of good people. "Because only the life of a person is perfected with both natural light and spiritual wisdom," he says. While thinking about modernism, he analyzes and criticizes several works written in the direction of modernism. According to him, man is the highest being. He condemns it to be beaten to the ground, to bring humanity to the lowest level. He says that one should not read the sweetest blessing called life on black paper and show its depressed and sad state, one should not forget how great a blessing it is, moreover, in some works written in the modernist spirit, the word is ugly. Criticizes works that use rhymes, use unpleasant allusions, and create a pessimistic impression on the reader instead of aesthetic pleasure.

"Among living creatures, only man reads books. The need to live by taking spiritual food from the book is a huge boundary that separates the human race from the animal world. If this limit is violated and a person is completely deprived of

spirituality, he will go back to the world of animal desires," says the writer in his article.

Pirmkul Kadirov's journalistic and scientific articles serve as a valuable resource for the people of literature and science until today. Above, we got acquainted with his most controversial article. But the writer has several other scientific and journalistic articles, which should be studied, analyzed, and the ideas contained in them should be used in appropriate places. Such creative products are published in many Soviet-era and post-independence periodicals and scientific journals of our country, especially "Literature and Art of Uzbekistan", "Tashkent Evening", "Hurriyat Newspapers", "Eastern Star", "Til and Literary education" magazines published literary-critical, journalistic articles and interviews. In conclusion, we can say that Pirmkul Kadirov's works, treatises, and articles written as a literary critic and abiyotologist deserve deep study today. After all, it is not wrong to say that studying not only the artistic works of writers in literature, but also their scientific, literary and critical views, scientific and journalistic articles, and passing them on to the next generation is one of the important issues facing our literature. Because the aesthetic ideal of the creator, the creative concept of the writer finds its reflection in all creative products: whether it is an artistic work or a scientific one; be it a journalistic article or a literary-critical one...

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